

Laser ultrasonic monitoring of the elastic properties of an apple

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Abstract:

Fruit firmness estimates usually require contacting or destructive methods. However, we propose to estimate firmness from an all optical, non-contacting method that generates and detects elastic waves in an apple. The compressional and shear wave velocities are governed by the fruit's elastic constants and density, which can be used to estimate firmness, non-destructively. High energy pulses of light are used to excite elastic waves via thermo-elastic expansion. Elastic waves are detected using a laser Doppler vibrometer. By exciting the apple surface at many locations we accurately estimate the compressional, shear and Rayleigh wave velocities of an apple. Repeated realizations of this experiment over 15 days to observe changes in apple elastic properties over time. Softening of the apple decreases the resonant mode frequencies and elastic constants, as well as increases wave attenuation. We find that attenuation is the most sensitive parameter to the aging of the apple. We believe that our novel method of apple interrogation could be automated, and extended to other fruits.

Background

Optical absorption spectrum and scattering of light in fruit have been used to non-destructively infer fruit soluble solid content [Peng and Lu, 2007] and texture [Lu and Peng, 2006, Huang and Lu, 2010]. Several other methods test the firmness of fruit, both at the point of harvest and periodically in cold storage, as an indicator of fruit quality. Magness-Taylor (MT) pressure tests involve a small cylindrical rod being pushed into the fruit until permanent deformation occurs. In addition to these destructive methods, non-destructive tests exist which measure the frequency of an apple's vibrational modes, which can be used to infer elastic properties [Cooke and Rand, 1973, Abbott et al., 1968, Lu and Abbott, 1996, Zhang et al., 2014]. We present elastic wave field measurements and a quantitative analysis of an intact apple using an optical system, which is non-contacting and non-destructive. Laser ultrasonic techniques [Scruby and Drain, 1990, Blum et al., 2010, Hitchman et al., 2015] are used to generate and detect the elastic waves in the apple, overcoming many of the limitations associated with contacting resonant experiments. To quantitatively estimate the apple's elastic properties, we use a high-energy pulsed laser to generate elastic waves in an apple via thermoelastic expansion, and a laser Doppler interferometer to detect elastic waves. Such a system has been successfully used in geophysics [e.g., Adam et al., 2014, Blum et al., 2013] and medical imaging [e.g., Johnson et al., 2014], but has not previously been applied to fruit.

Methods

Figure 1 shows a cross section of the apple during excitation and the propagation of the generated surface Rayleigh waves and compressional waves (P-wave). A high energy laser pulse absorbed by the sample creates a localized area of rapidly increased temperature, and hence increased volume (i.e., thermo-elastic expansion), producing elastic waves [Scruby and Drain, 1990]. Our source of elastic waves is a pulsed laser with center wavelength of 1730 nm, pulse energy of 17 mJ, pulse duration of 10 ns and a repetition rate of 20 Hz. We limit pulse energy and repetition rate of the laser to not damage the apple during excitation. Elastic waves are detected using a home built optical heterodyne interferometer called a laser Doppler vibrometer (LDV) [Hitchman et al., 2015]. The LDV measures surface particle velocity (in mm/s) in the direction of the laser beam by detecting the Doppler shift of light backscattered by the sample [Scruby and Drain, 1990, Hitchman et al., 2015].

LDVs have previously been used to detect the surface motion of fruit stimulated using a contacting source [Terasaki et al., 2006]. Excitation and detection of elastic waves using lasers offers several advantages over contacting transducer methods; namely the removal of source to sample coupling inconsistencies, small source and receiver footprint, and ease of scanning. LDV signal quality is aided by retro-reflective tape applied to the apple.

Results

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Figure 1. Cross-section of an apple to illustrate that laser-generated elastic body- and surface-waves are detected with a laser Doppler vibrometer.

For an isotropic medium, two elastic constants and the density define elastic wave propagation. Often such media are represented by the elastic or Young's modulus, E , and the Poisson's ratio, ν , where the former describes the amount of strain when stress is applied in the same dimension, while the latter is the ratio between the strain in orthogonal directions from stress [e.g., Stein and Wyssession, 2009]. The shear wave velocity v_s , P-wave velocity v_p and density ρ uniquely define the elastic moduli for an isotropic medium:

$$E = v_s^2 \rho \left(\frac{v_p^2}{v_s^2} - 2 \right), \nu = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{v_p^2}{v_s^2} - 1 \right) \quad (1)$$

We quantitatively estimate E and ν from the propagation speeds of P-, shear, and surface waves generated in a 189 g New Zealand Braeburn apple. Its density is $901 \pm 1 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and the circumference is 24 cm. The wavefield as a function of time and distance (Figure 2) is dominated by surface waves circling the apple multiple times. A band-pass filter with corner frequencies of 50 and 6000 Hz was applied to highlight the lowest order resonant modes of the apple. From the propagation of these surface waves, we estimate that the Rayleigh wave speed is $v_R = 100.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ m/s}$. The earliest part of the same waveforms highlight the lower-amplitude arrival of the P-waves. A linear regression on this arrival results in a P-wave speed estimate $v_p = 182 \pm 7 \text{ m/s}$.

Figure 2. Elastic wave elds as a function of time and angular distance are dominated by Rayleigh waves circumnavigating the apple as zig-zagging linear features in the record.

Due to limitations of typical LDVs, shear waves are not easily detected directly, unless a multicomponent LDV is used [Blum et al., 2010]. Instead, we calculate v_s from the P-wave and Rayleigh wave speeds resulting in an estimate of $v_s = 110.4$ m/s using Equation 4 from Hitchman et al. [2016]. Using equation 1 we find quantitative estimates of the elastic modulus $E = 26 \pm 1.5$ MPa, and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.21 \pm 0.05$. The resonant modes of a system are the result of interfering propagating waves. The frequency of the fundamental mode, f , closely matches previously presented values measured using contacting methods at comparable frequencies [Chen and DeBaerdemaeker, 1993] and has been used to infer apple firmness via the Firmness Index, FI:

$$FI = f^2 m^{\frac{2}{3}}$$

where m is the mass of the fruit. Chen and DeBaerdemaeker [1993] show that FI is proportional to the Elastic modulus, E . The estimated elastic modulus $E = 26 \pm 1.5$ MPa, however, does not match previously reported measurements using compressive or destructive methods performed on apple esh sections [Khan and Vincent, 1993, Varela et al., 2007], as these are performed at quasi-static conditions. The apple esh is viscoelastic, and thus exhibits frequency dependence of its elastic properties [Varela et al., 2007].

Figure 3. Wavefields in an apple at a constant source-receiver epicentral distance of 173 indicate a decrease in velocity and an increase in attenuation over a period of 360 hours.

Furthermore, we estimate changes in the elastic and anelastic properties over 15 days from elastic waves recorded and detected daily at a source and receiver separation of 173 degrees. Figure 3 shows the time-lapse elastic wave forms. Changes in the arrival time and amplitude of the elastic waves show a decrease in the elastic moduli. The wavefields of Figure 3 clearly show primary and surface waves arriving consistently later (and decreasing in amplitude). From the estimated density and elastic wave speeds the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio were estimated as the apple aged. A least-squares regression on the daily estimates of E in panel 2 of Figure 4 indicates a decay rate of $\delta E = 0.355 \pm 0.005$ MPa/d, which amounts to a 19% decrease over the fifteen day period. Similarly the decay rate of the Ffirmness Index in panel 1 was estimated to be $\delta FI = 3336 \pm 3$ Hz²/kg²⁼³/d, which amounts to an overall decrease of 30%. The Poisson's ratio was not found to decrease significantly.

The amplitude of Rayleigh waves of Figure 3 decay monotonically and significantly as the apple ages. Tracking the amplitude of the phase with the largest amplitude at $t = 0$ hours, panel 3 of Figure 4 results in a decrease rate of $\delta A = 240 \pm 70$ nm/s/d, or 75% after 15 days. The Rayleigh wave amplitude was found to decrease at a significantly greater rate than E and may provide the most sensitive parameter of elastic monitoring of the ripeness of an apple.

Figure 4. Elastic modulus and Rayleigh wave amplitude are estimated over a period of fifteen days. Error bars show the standard error in each property from initial measurements.

Conclusions

Fully non-contacting and non-destructive elastic measurements on a Braeburn apple using laser ultrasound provide the means to monitor the ripeness of the fruit. The most sensitive parameter to monitor the ripeness of the apple is the attenuation of Rayleigh waves in the apple, decreasing 75% in 15 days. This approach to apple quality monitoring needs to be tested on a range of apples and to be made faster before it can be introduced in a commercial setting.

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